

NURSING CARE OF PATIENTS WITH DUODENAL ULCER

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Summary

Peptic ulcer disease is one of the most common gastrointestinal disease worldwide. The prevalence of peptic ulcer disease is now so large that it has entailed the development of diagnostic and treatment methods improve. Currently used drug combination may produce effects even at 80% of cases, which is virtually unheard of in any other disease entity. Over 60% of peptic ulcers are located in the duodenum (3-4 times more than in the stomach). Estimates suggest that 5-10% of adults are affected by duodenal ulcer, and it occurs three times more often in men than in women. In children, it occurs less frequently, but in 2% of adult onset is given in childhood [11].

The aim of this study was to learn the importance and role of nurses in patient care duodenal ulcer. The job of research problems adopted five major research questions: 1. What is the level of knowledge about the patient's duodenal ulcer? 2. Do you know the cause of his illness? 3. Do you know the method of treatment of duodenal ulcer? 4. What information and support measures are expected from the nurse at the time of treatment? 5. What is the involvement of patients in the active participation of relapse prevention and healthy lifestyle after treatment?

In this work the method has been applied case study involving the analysis of individual human lives caught up in certain situations on the analysis of education or specific educational phenomena of nature, through the prism of individual biography with a focus on human development for the diagnosis or phenomena in order to take therapeutic measures [2]. The collection of research material used for work the following research techniques: observation, interview, document, documentation and analysis [3, 4, 5, 6]. In this work the message gained from your observation of the patient and his medical history.

The study was conducted in the Public Health Care in the Outpatient Clinic in Koziencice family doctor. The marketing research was a patient who was admitted to the doctor to diagnosis pain upper right quadrant of the abdomen. The patient lived 45 years in Koziencice, has been married for 24 years, has two children, lives in a detached house, housing is very good. He works as a teacher. The role of nurses in addressing patients with duodenal ulcer. The purpose of nursing a patient with duodenal ulcer is to assist in overcoming problems and promoting preventive measures, minimization of unpleasant experiences and feelings, and their neutralization by the use of appropriate treatments, education, psychological support and physical health. Home care also ensures the transfer of clear and tailored to patients' knowledge of information that helped to overcome fears and doubts related to treatment [7].

The patient was correctly diagnosed and treated. Problems of nursing care have been identified and properly planned. Action Care has been implemented in accordance with the plan of nursing care undertaken. You and your family are prepared to conduct normal life. The aim of this study was to determine the scope of care for a patient with duodenal ulcer. The essence of nursing is the provision of professional nursing, education in duodenal ulcer and prevent complications. On the basis of discussions with the patient, I can say that they have some knowledge of the duodenal ulcer, but this knowledge is incomplete and need further education in this field. She knows the cause of his illness and is fully convinced about the effectiveness of treatment and the importance of a healthy lifestyle. She does not know everything about the treatment of duodenal ulcer. Patient education has contributed to increasing the scope of knowledge on the subject. We are happy to read literature by registered, highly estimated the press as a good source of information. On the basis of patient interview has deficiencies within the meaning of the importance of diet in duodenal ulcer. Action to raise awareness of the patient, caused that is fully satisfied with the changes in diet and the positive impact of diet. The conversation, sense of security and emotional support allow the patient to accept the health situation. The nurse is a person who because of their profession is committed to providing support. She is fully convinced of the health behaviors in shaping health and empowerment. He feels responsible for her health and life. It turns out to understand the importance of a healthy lifestyle after treatment. Is prepared to deal with cases of doubt associated with the disease.

Conclusion

1. She has received satisfactory information on her duodenal ulcer. 2. The patient was transferred to an optimal level of knowledge about the causes of the disease, we would read the literature by registered mail. 3. Discussed in detail with the patient treatment of the disease. 4. Patient transmission of meaningful information related to the treatment allowed the patient to accept the situation. Nursing actions enabled the change in approach to the problem. 5. She has been working in the diagnostic and therapeutic and beauty, health prevention has the proper attitude. It turns out an understanding as to the advisability of modifications to the current mode of life, strengthening and raising the level of health.

Introduction

Peptic ulcer disease is one of the most common gastrointestinal disease worldwide. The prevalence of peptic ulcer disease is now so large that it has entailed the development of diagnostic and treatment methods improve. Currently used drug combination may produce effects even at 80% of cases, which is virtually unheard of in any other disease entity. Over 60% of peptic ulcers are located in the duodenum (3-4 times more than in the stomach). Estimates suggest that 5-10% of adults are affected by duodenal ulcer, and it occurs three times more often in men than in women. In children, it occurs less frequently, but in 2% of adult onset is given in childhood [11].

In epidemiological studies on the prevalence of peptic ulcer disease in children seen constant growth of the number of cases and increasing its presence in increasingly younger children. In the first years of life of gastric and duodenal ulcers occur with similar frequency, after 6 years of age dominated by duodenal ulcers. Duodenal ulcer in boys compared with girls is from 1.5 to 4.5 times more often. From the 50s the last century in developed countries of Western Europe and North

America the incidence of duodenal ulcer gradually decreases and the incidence of gastric ulcers is rather constant with a slight increase, translated the increased use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) [11]. Despite progress in the treatment of peptic ulcer disease complications such as percentage of hemorrhage or perforation has not declined, in the case of stomach ulcers even increased [1].

Peptic ulcer usually causes symptoms of the gastrointestinal tract, but may be asymptomatic, especially in the elderly, and then it is usually associated with NSAIDs. Cardinal symptom of peptic ulcer is pain in the abdomen with a blunt (crushing or burning) usually occurs 2-3 hours after meal intake. The more distal the location of the ulcer in the upper gastrointestinal tract, including the later of the ingested meal starts with pain that occurs with an empty stomach. For duodenal ulcer are typical or night hunger pains wake patient from sleep. Reduces the severity of their pain after a meal or taking alkalis. Epigastric pain is not specific for peptic ulcer disease. Less than half of patients with typical ulcer pain is active peptic ulcer [8]. Typical pain, night awakening from sleep occurs in 2 / 3 cases of duodenal ulcer in 1 / 3 of stomach ulcer, but in one third of cases of dyspepsia without ulcer. Ulcer pain may be accompanied by dyspeptic symptoms: bloating, belching, epigastric fullness or early satiety, intolerance to fatty meals. However, only in 20-25% of patients with dyspeptic symptoms are diagnosed with peptic ulcer [9]. Sometimes patients also indicate nausea, chest discomfort, anorexia and / or weight loss. Physical examination of uncomplicated peptic ulcer can be at most state or percussion pain on pressure in the upper abdomen. It is worth remembering alarm symptoms suggestive of complications of peptic ulcer or ulcer cancer, which include: weight loss > 10% within 3 months, repeated vomiting, dysphagia, anemia, gastrointestinal bleeding (haematemesis, bloody or tarry stools) palpation tumor in the abdomen. The basic procedure in the diagnosis of peptic ulcer disease is endoscopic examination of upper gastrointestinal tract, allowing an ulcer and download show segments for the diagnosis of H. pylori infection and histological examination. Gastroscopy may also show changes with a history of peptic ulcer in the form of scars after ulcer or distortion after ulcer duodenal bulb. Although symptoms suggestive of peptic ulcer disease may constitute up to 40% of the indications for endoscopy, peptic ulcer is rarely recognized only slightly more than 6% of all endoscopy [10]. Endoscopic almost completely supplanted radiography of the upper gastrointestinal tract in diagnosis of peptic ulcer disease, but we must remember that its diagnostic accuracy in the case of peptic ulcer larger than 5 mm using the double contrast technique by an experienced radiologist, is similar to endoscopy. Radiographs of upper gastrointestinal peptic ulcer documenting archival material are perfect to use when deciding whether eradication of H. pylori in patients currently without active ulcer, but infected with H. pylori [11].

Aim

Aim of this study was to investigate the importance of the role of nurses in the care of a patient treated for duodenal ulcer. In this paper, the research was adopted as a matter of five major research questions: 1 What is the level of knowledge about the patient's duodenal ulcer? 2. Do you know the cause of his illness? 3. Do you know the method of treatment of duodenal ulcer? 4. What information and support measures are expected from the nurse at the time of treatment? 5. What is the involvement of patients in the active participation of relapse prevention and healthy lifestyle after treatment?

Methods, techniques and tools

The paper has been used method consists of individual case analysis of individual human lives caught up in certain situations or on an analysis of educational developments in the specific educational, through the prism of individual biography with a focus on human development for the diagnosis or phenomena in order to take therapeutic measures [2]. The collection of research material used for work the following research techniques: observation, interview, document analysis and documentation from your observation of the patient and his history of the disease [3, 4, 5, 6].

Characteristics and course of study

The study was conducted in the Public Health Care in the Outpatient Clinic in Kozenice

family doctor. The marketing research was a patient who was admitted to the doctor to diagnosis pain upper right quadrant of the abdomen.

The patient lived 45 years in Kozienice, has been married for 24 years, has two children, lives in a detached house, housing is very good. He works as a teacher. The work he does gives her great satisfaction and contentment, and at the same time causes stress situations. In the past, childhood disease are inflammation of the parotid, smallpox, measles, rubella, frequent tonsillitis and colds. As a teenager practiced long-distance running, her health was very good. During long-term work very emotionally responsive to problems of youth, is a person who, for any student trying to get individually. The patient began to experience pain in the upper abdomen on the right side, which intensified especially 1-2 hours after meals. Observed that food hates pain, and hunger pains occur at night. Generally good condition of the patient, correct body structure, logical thinking, growth 164 cm, mass 67 kg, normal verbal, RR - 115/70, pulse 84. Respiratory efficiency the number of breaths correct, do not smoke cigarettes, look - he wears glasses, hearing - normal, skin - clean, free of efflorescence. Digestive system - correct body structure, your mouth clean, full of teeth. There are pain in the upper abdomen on the right side. During the pain, the patient complains of lack of appetite, irregular bowel movements. Urinary system - do not give any irregularities in the functioning of this system. Bone-joint - correct, is a smooth, moving alone. The mental condition of the patient - is a positive attitude to life, loves his job and take the treatment as soon as possible to eliminate the symptoms of the disease. Her husband and children support the patient during treatment, it can count on their help in every situation. The first symptoms of disease present in a patient appeared at the beginning of March 2009. Experienced severe pain, feeling of bloating, pain in the night (hunger). These problems appeared after stress and after a sharp intake of foods and drinking coffee. During a violent attack of pain the patient went to the doctor. After examination by a physician received intramuscular injections, analgesics, and pain after resolution of the attack to come home. It was recommended laboratory tests and a blood test for the presence of *Helicobacter pylori*. She also received a referral for an ultrasound of the abdominal cavity and gastroscopy. After doing research, which showed the presence of duodenal ulcers and *Helicobacter pylori*, the patient was subjected to pharmacological leceniu. It was recommended first-line therapy: Omeprazole 20 mg 2 x, 2 x 1000 mg Amoxicillin, Klacid 2 x 500 mg. Treatment continued for 7 days. It was also recommended dietary therapy. Diet in peptic ulcer opera on moderation, balance of products, ease of assimilation, and is intended to protect the damaged mucosa. Important in the treatment of duodenal ulcer is to ensure adequate calorie meals, regular consumption of smaller portions (5-6 meals a day, every 2-3 hours). Avoid eating heavy meals, coffee, drugs that increase gastric acid secretion. The patient is under the care of the family doctor.

The role of nurses in addressing patients with duodenal ulcer. The purpose of nursing a patient with duodenal ulcer is to assist in overcoming problems and promoting preventive measures, minimization of unpleasant experiences and feelings, and their neutralization by the use of appropriate treatments, education, psychological support and physical [7]. Home care also ensures the transfer of clear and tailored to patients' knowledge of information that helped to overcome fears and doubts related to treatment.

Nursing Issues [2, 7, 11]

1. Upper abdominal pain caused by irritation of the ulcer niche. The aim of care is to alleviate pain and gastric acid neutralization. These objectives have been achieved through: application to the attending physician of drugs that inhibit the production of hydrochloric acid and neutralizing stomach acid, to prepare the patient for gastroscopy and download material for other diagnostic tests (on the order of a physician), the order of a physician for antibiotic treatment because of the presence of *Helicobacter pylori* observation of the patient towards the intensification of the pain, the definition of intensity, duration and location of pain, administration of analgesics as prescribed, monitoring of medications, establish contact with the patient to obtain cooperation, explain the need to avoid patient medication, drugs that increase gastric acid secretion, ill explain the need to avoid stress and excessive exercise, and discharge of strong emotional tensions,

facilitate contact with a psychotherapist. On this basis the pain subsided partially and improved patient well-being.

2. The deficit of knowledge about the disease, its symptoms and complications. For the nursing activities in this area should be patient education in the field of duodenal ulcer by means of: an assessment of the patient areas of knowledge about the disease, transmission of patient knowledge of anatomy, physiology and the role of the duodenum in the digestive system, discuss the causes of the disease, a discussion of existing symptoms, types of possible complications, provide educational materials about the disease (medical literature, flyers, brochures, guides), supporting a patient in cases of doubt associated with the disease, allowing contact with the doctor. On this basis the patient transferred to an optimal level of knowledge about the nature of the disease, the patient happy to read literature by registered mail.

3. Discomfort associated with the occurrence of dyspeptic symptoms: epigastric fullness, belching, feeling of dryness in the mouth. For nursing activities should be: to reduce the unpleasant feelings and normalize peristalsis. Achieve the above objectives by: demonstrating an understanding of the problems of patients, to evaluate symptoms, clarification of how the patient is highly influenced by the nature and timing of food and drugs on the occurrence of symptoms from the digestive system, showing ill effects on the body due to poor selection of food, read a patient with the difference of diet, depending on the stage of disease, drawing attention to the precise chewing food, quiet eating food, using herbs to improve bowel motility (peppermint, St. John's wort), taking care of the hydration of the mucous membranes of the mouth (oral fluid), the maintenance of oral hygiene, encouraging the washing oral tisane (mint, chamomile), discuss with the patient capacity to cope in the event of dyspeptic symptoms with the difficulties resulting from the disease. These actions led to a reduction in nursing dyspeptic symptoms.

4. Decreased levels of mood caused by the diagnosis and treatment of duodenal ulcer. The purpose for this activity is to help the patient in the acceptance of the disease and treatment through: an interview with the patient about the unacceptable situation of mental health patients convinced to cooperate in the process of diagnosis - treatment - nursing care, psychological assistance, to create a friendly atmosphere and sense of security, encourage conversation and express their concerns, to discuss measures to facilitate the change in approach to the problem. By applying these measures have improved the mood, the patient began to express their fears, accept your health situation.

5. The reluctance to change their existing diet. The aim in this regard is the mobilization of the patient to change diet and convinced of the need to follow a diet. These objectives can be achieved by: assessing the level of knowledge of the patient and family about dietary recommendations in duodenal ulcer, determine the scope of cooperation with the patient, providing information about the positive impact of diet, talk about past habits, discuss with the patient and her family's main recommendations diet.

The main dietary recommendations during the treatment period are: light diet - with reduced amounts of animal fats and vegetable fibers, regular, frequent eating of meals - about 5 times a day, avoiding high-fiber vegetables structural - such as cabbage, asparagus stalks, avoiding consumption of salt and spicy foods, avoid fried foods, avoid acting meteorismical products - for example, dry legumes, cooking food in water or steamed, and then bake in aluminum foil, sipping water, medicines, because there is a risk of interactions between antibiotics and substances contained such . the juices (flavonoids) and dairy products (calcium), which may weaken the action of antibiotics and increase the risk of side effects, stop drinking, provide educational materials about the diet in duodenal ulcer, showing a patient that the diagnosis of duodenal ulcer requires from it a discipline in lifestyle and behavior health treatment, according to a discussion of diet and the occurrence of dyspeptic symptoms, dietary modifications indicated directions. Through these activities the patient possessed the necessary knowledge about the diet in duodenal ulcer and accepted the transferred knowledge and apply the recommendations.

6. Anxiety about returning to work. The objectives of the action in this regard is to alleviate anxiety by: discussing the negative impact of stress on duodenal ulcer disease, patient education on

how to cope with stress (work of breathing, relaxation, music therapy, exercise, yoga, walks, plenty of sleep), the development of ability to communicate effectively with students, discussion of assertive behavior, the motivation to maintain the assertive, show the beneficial impact of distancing themselves from the problem, discuss the importance of overcoming their own time (scheduling of classes in school, plan to work from home, the early preparation of materials for classes, checking the work of time), an explanation of how stress is manifested in patients (implementation of autoresponse), the patient was motivated to form but change the approach to return to work, to enable contact with a psychologist. With these treatments, the patient was educated to cope with stress.

7. The possibility of complications due to healed ulcer niche. The aim here is to eradication of ulcer and the ability to capture symptoms suggestive of complications by: patient awareness about the need to complete the antibiotic treatment and regular use of prescribed drugs in duodenal ulcer, discussion of the characteristic signs of the development of complications in duodenal ulcer, an indication of the positive aspects of patient knowledge on the proper conduct of the health, provide guidance on self-observation for the occurrence of complications of duodenal ulcer, awareness of the need to immediately consult a doctor if you are experiencing alarming symptoms (severe abdominal pain, dark stools), to educate patients to reduce anxiety and coping the difficulties resulting from illness, a patient showing of harm to non-steroidal anti-inflammatory on the mucosa of the duodenum, to support patients in cases of doubt associated with the disease, mobilizing for regular visits to the doctor gastroenterologist, internist. Thanks to the activities in patient complications did not occur.

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Conclusions

1. The patient has received satisfactory information on her duodenal ulcer.
2. The patient was transferred to an optimal level of knowledge about the causes of the disease, we would read the literature by registered mail.
3. Discussed in detail with the patient treatment of the disease.
4. Patient transmission of meaningful information related to the treatment allowed the patient to accept the situation. Nursing actions enabled the change in approach to the problem.
5. She has been working in the diagnostic and therapeutic and beauty, health prevention has the proper attitude. It turns out an understanding as to the advisability of modifications to the current mode of life, strengthening and raising the level of health.

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